

Zero Trust-oriented Quality Attribute Scenarios (QAS)

This document consolidates the QAS scenarios derived by the method. Each scenario follows the template: source, stimulus, artifact, environment, response, response measure and preserves traceability to ASR/QA, ZT principles, and mechanisms (A* IDs).

1. Mechanism legend (subset used in the case)

ID	Mechanism (from the paper)	Associated ZT principle(s) (e.g.)
A11	Continuous Authentication	Verify Explicitly
A3	Lightweight Mutual Authentication (mTLS)	Verify Explicitly
A16	Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)	Verify Explicitly; Least-Privilege Access
A13	Fine-Grained Security Policies	Least-Privilege Access
A8	Micro-segmentation	Assume Breach
A6	TLS-encrypted Communication	Assume Breach
A10	Sandbox	Assume Breach

SI_1 – Integrity (ASR_1)

Field	Content
ASR/QA	ASR_1 – Integrity (secondary)
ZT Principles	Verify Explicitly; Least-Privilege Access
Source	Access control service
Stimulus	An entity attempts to access a protected resource
Artifact	Authentication and authorization subsystem
Environment	Normal operation
Response	The system performs continuous authentication (A11) and evaluates ABAC (A16) rules enforced through fine-grained policies (A13) before granting access.
Response measure	Requests are granted only if identity and attributes satisfy the policies; all others are denied and recorded as an access decision.

SC_1 – Confidentiality (ASR_1)

Field	Content
ASR/QA	ASR_1 – Confidentiality (primary)
ZT Principles	Verify Explicitly; Least-Privilege Access; Assume Breach
Source	Sending service
Stimulus	A service-to-service request carrying sensitive data is issued
Artifact	Inter-service communication channel and execution environment
Environment	Inter-service communication under potential compromise
Response	The system isolates services with micro-segmentation (A8), enforces lightweight mTLS (A3), and establishes TLS-encrypted (A6) channels. Optionally, it executes sensitive processing within a sandbox (A10).
Response measure	Only authenticated services within authorized segments can exchange messages; transmitted data remains confidential and unaltered; the impact of compromised components is limited.

SA_1 – Auditability (ASR_2)

Field	Content
ASR/QA	ASR_2 – Auditability (primary)
ZT Principles	Verify Explicitly; Least-Privilege Access; Assume Breach
Source	Monitoring and logging service
Stimulus	A security-relevant action occurs (e.g., access decision, privilege change, or policy update)

Artifact	Audit logging and monitoring pipeline
Environment	Normal operation under potential compromise
Response	The system records identity-attributed audit events in a centralized log, correlates events to detect anomalies, and stores trails in an append-only/immutable repository to provide tamper evidence.
Response measure	Events are complete, attributable, and tamper-evident; anomalies are detected and alerted within an acceptable detection window.

SV_1 – Availability (ASR_3)

Field	Content
ASR/QA	ASR_3 – Availability (primary)
ZT Principles	Verify Explicitly; Least-Privilege Access; Assume Breach
Source	External actor or compromised workload
Stimulus	An abnormal/malicious request pattern targets a critical endpoint and causes localized overload
Artifact	Service boundary, inter-service channel, and execution environment
Environment	Degraded operation under potential compromise
Response	Isolate affected services using micro-segmentation (A8), preserve secure communication via TLS (A6), and contain untrusted execution with sandbox (A10) to prevent propagation.
Response measure	Critical services remain available within SLO thresholds under degradation; disruption is contained to authorized segments; and secure communication is maintained.